

Parents' Engagement in the Learning Process of Senior High School Students in Selected Sisters of St. Paul Chartres-Owned Schools in the Philippines

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Abstract

The study sought to evaluate the extent of engagement of parents of senior high school students enrolled in selected Sisters of St. Paul Chartres-owned schools in the Philippines. Survey was conducted to 260 parents to examine the extent of their engagement in the learning process of their children. The data gathered were treated using descriptive statistics. Based on the results, the extent of family involvement in selected St. Paul Schools in terms of parenting and communicating were very high. Parents engagement in the learning process was immanent in the realm of parenting and communicating. On the other hand, the extent of family involvement in terms of volunteering, learning at home, decision making and collaborating with the community were high. Rooms for improvement are still needed for the identified aspects of parent's engagement. Results were utilized to serve as foundation in the development of parent engagement program for selected St. Paul of Chartres owned schools in the Philippines.

Keywords: parent engagement; learning process; senior high school student; Sisters of St. Paul Chartres-Owned Schools

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INTRODUCTION

Parent engagement in the learning process of the students is significant to affect student learning. Parents are considered as learning companions at home and learning collaborators of teachers in school. However, challenges are inevitable in affecting student learning in the 21st century learning environment. The engagement of parents are influenced by the status and condition that they are experiencing. The advancement of technology and the disruptive events situate the parents, schools and learners into a new environment where it opens new doors for opportunities and challenges. Student learning is achieved through the engagement of parents in the learning process. The parent engagement both at home and at school strengthen learning performance of the learners because of the connectivity of home and school towards the education of the learners (Hendersen & Mapp, 2002). However, the success of the engagement of parents lies on the commitment and dedication of parents to actively support and engage in the learning

process of the students (Taylor et al., 2004). Furthermore, for Barton et al., (2004), parent engagement is not just limited to supporting the school operations especially in educating their children but having the capability to initiatively engage in whatever means do parents have at home and in their locality. Hence, parents play a vital role of being the prime mover in engaging to the learning process of their children.

The study aimed to evaluate the engagement of parents in selected St. Paul of Chartres owned schools in Philippines based on the following aspects:

1. *Parenting.* Parenting is a form of parental involvement that hone the home environment of the learners and at the same time strengthens the relationship of all the members of the family. It is a type of parental involvement that gives care and support to the learners for them to have a conducive home learning environment. It strengthens the bond of the families and improve their support system at home.

2. *Communicating.* Communicating is a type of parental involvement that creates effective modes of communication between school and home where the parents and teachers exchange information about the learning progress of the students at home and in school.
3. *Volunteering.* Volunteering is about having parents support the school endeavors. It is a type of parental involvement that fosters the active participation of parents towards school operations and to collaboratively work with the teachers in school and the communities in the local community. A service-oriented approach in the engagement practices of parents to the learning process of the learners. Volunteering is an act of free will where an individual is not expecting of something in return. In other words, it is an act out of volition to help and provide service for the betterment of others (Gromav, 2011).
4. *Learning at Home.* Learning at home is a form of parental involvement that highlights the support given by the family to the learners at home. The learning home environment is established for the children to have a progressive learning experience at home.
5. *Decision Making.* making is a form of parental involvement that empowers parents to be leaders and for them to actively participate in school decision-making. A type of parental involvement that empowers the parents to lead and participate in school decision-making.
6. *Collaborating with the Community.* Collaborating with the community is a type of parental involvement that supports given to the learning experience of the students through the active participation of the communities - the local government units, private organizations and religious groups - to school programs and activities.

LITERATURES

Epstein's six types of involvement highlight the opportunities for parents to engage in the learning experience of the learners. Parents are given a significant role in the formation of the children towards quality education (Gülcan and Duran, 2018). The active engagement of parents serves as an avenue for them to realize their accountability and responsibility for the education of their children. Parental involvement centers on the success and meaningful learning experience of the learners. The involvement of the parents ensures that learners are taken care and supported to their individual endeavors in life.

Parenting. A type of parental involvement that gives care and support to the learners for them to have a conducive home learning environment. Parenting improves the relationship of the learners to each member of the family. In other words, it strengthens families to improve the support system at home. Epstein (2009) suggests that home environment should be nourished to serve as the safe learning space for children. In addition, she encourages parents to continuously equip themselves with necessary understanding and skills towards parenting their children.

Communicating. Communicating is one of the parental involvements that creates effective modes of communication between school and home where the parents and teachers exchange information about the learning progress of the students at home and in school. Parents become collaborative with the teachers and other stakeholders when there is a good line of communication. Information that are well communicated from school to home and vice-versa fosters mutual understanding among the stakeholders. Besides, school policies and the learning progress of the students need to be communicated clearly to prevent issues and problems to occur. Constant communication about the learning performance of the children both at home and in school and keeping the parents updated of school programs are the things to observe in communicating (Epstein, 2009; Harris, 2019).

Volunteering. Volunteering is a parental involvement that fosters active participation of parents in the operation of school. The spirit of volunteerism is realized through the collaborative effort of teachers and parents in recruiting and organizing parent help and support (Epstein, 2019). Volunteering is a service-oriented approach in the engagement of parents in the learning process of the learners. Moreover, this is an event that gives opportunity for the parents to share their talents, skills and resources for the betterment of the school. Parents' volunteerism is realized through being an active collaborator of teachers in delivering the learning instruction for the learners and the contribution that parents give to the sustainability of the operation of school (Durisic and Bunijevac, 2017).

Learning at Home. A type of parental involvement that allows the family to provide support to the learning experience of the learners at home. Furthermore, learning at home establishes a culture of excellence and discipline for the academic growth in the family. The learnings that students acquired in school are authentically applied at home through the support and assistance given by the family. The kind of learning experience that students have at home greatly influence their well-being (Treviño et al., 2021). The learning at home behavior and experience of the learners reflects the kind of education they acquired from school (Durisic and Bunijevac, 2017). Hence, the learning home environment is established for the children to have a progressive learning experience at home.

Decision Making. Decision Making is a type of parental involvement that empowers the parents to lead and participate in school decision-making. Parents are given the voice to be part of the decision making of the school. It includes having the parents participate in school decision making and foster parent leaders and representatives who are willing to contribute their time and effort for the betterment of the institution (Durisic and Bunijevac, 2017). The sense of ownership is developed among the parents if they will be immersed to the Paulinian culture especially if

they will be part of the decision making. Besides, the involvement of parents in the decision-making process creates a significant impact to other stakeholders (Hicks, 2012). Decision making is an involvement of parents in the administrative and managerial aspect of school operation.

Collaborating with the Community. Collaborating with the community is one of the types of parental involvement that allows the participation of the community in the learning experience of the students through the collaborative effort of the school and the parents of the learners. Furthermore, support is given to the learning experience of the students through the active participation of the communities such as the local government units, private organizations and religious groups - to school programs and activities (Durisic and Bunijevac, 2017). The programs of the local government unit are actively participated by the school community and in the same manner, the school programs and events are supported by the local communities. Hence, the involvement of parents in making the school and community harmoniously collaborating with each other gain positive results especially to the learning experience of the learners.

METHODS

The study used a descriptive quantitative research approach in evaluating the engagement of parents in the learning process of the students. This study was conducted in selected St. Paul Schools administered by Sisters of St. Paul of Chartres in Luzon, Visayas and Mindanao. The participating schools were as follows: 1) St. Paul Academy of Goa, Inc., 2) St. Paul School - Barotac Nuevo, 3) St. Paul School - Barotac Viejo, 4) St. Paul School of Buug, 5) St. Paul University Manila and 6) St. Paul University Surigao.

The study was participated in by the parents of the enrolled SHS students of the selected St. Paul of Chartres (SPC) owned schools in the Philippines. The study used convenient sampling for the selection of the participants considering the availability of the parents. As a

result, 260 parents participated in the study. The following are the breakdown: 11 parents from St. Paul School A, 45 parents from St. Paul School B, 26 parents from St. Paul School C, 6 parents from St. Paul School D, 35 parents from St. Paul School E, and 137 parents from St. Paul School F.

The researcher used the questionnaire developed by Kartika Yulianti, Mienke Droop and Eddie Denessen of Radboud University Nijmegen. The six facets of Epstein's parental involvement in the current research study have an alpha coefficient of .83. The result indicates that the scale in terms of internal consistency was relatively high. The modified questionnaire was presented to Joyce Epstein for validation. Joyce Epstein is the leading researcher on parental involvement. She is the director of the Center on School, Family, and Community Partnerships. Furthermore, she is a well-known professor of education in the Johns Hopkins University School of Education.

This research study upholds the highest ethical standards for the protection of the participants and the organizations that will be involved in this study. It was ensured that there was administrative clearance from the Office of the Dean of College of Education - Graduate School of St. Paul University Manila. Consent from the participants of the study was secured to respect their well-being, especially their privacy. Accordingly, the dignity and identity of the participants were protected by anonymizing the individual and organizational data and ensuring confidentiality to all information.

RESULTS

The extent of family involvement in selected St. Paul Schools in the Philippines are discussed in six aspects, namely, Parenting, Communicating, Volunteering, Learning at Home, Decision Making and Collaborating with the Community.

Parenting. Table 1 presents the engagement of parents in terms of parenting. Parent engagement in terms of parenting is interpreted as very high extent. In the Article 3 no. 3 of The Child and Youth Welfare Code of the Philippines,

it is stated that the children have the right to the basic needs such as having food to eat, clothes to wear and place to stay.

Table 1
Mean distribution of parents' engagement in terms of parenting. (n=260)

Parenting	Composite Mean	Interpretation
The parents fulfill their children's basic needs (food, clothing, and shelter).	3.84	Very High Extent
The parents make sure that their children attend school in compliance with all rules and regulations.	3.74	Very High Extent
The parents discuss the importance of good education with their child.	3.74	Very High Extent
The parents handle conflict with their children quite well.	3.44	Very High Extent
The parents supervise their children when they use mobile devices.	3.45	Very High Extent
Total	3.64	Very High Extent

*Legend: 1=Very low extent (1.00-1.75); 2=Low extent (1.76-2.50); 3=High extent (2.51-3.25); 4=Very high extent (3.26-4.00)

Parents are responsible of the well-being and personal development of their children until they become matured enough to take responsibility of their own lives (Ceka and Murati, 2016). Hatti (2021) argues that parents are the first educators of the learners since learning starts at home. Parents are the children's strongest role model because of the impact that they have in the lives of their children (Ceka and Murati, 2016). This is supported by Article 46 no. 6 of Child and Welfare Code of the Philippines where it is stated that parents have the duty and responsibility to form their children in accordance with what is morally good and right for their total well-being. Conflict management is an essential skill for parents to acquire especially when they immersed themselves in the learning process of their children. Conflict should be seen in a progressive perspective where problems and issues serve as open doors for improvement (Ruiz et. al, 2013).

Parents have the responsibility to monitor and supervise the usage of mobile devices of their children at home (Olafsson et. al., 2014 cited in Topper, 2017). Senate Bill No. 1271 also known as Regulated Use of Mobile Phones and Electronic Gadgets in Schools Act (2020) suggested that there is a need to balance this goal of increasing student performance to properly integrate the use of mobile devices and electronic gadgets in our educational system. Moreover, parents

need to protect their children from malicious activities online like cyberbullying and other forms of harassment (Varkley Foundation, 2020). Therefore, the proper use of technology at home could foster a stronger link between family culture and learning for the education continuum between school and home (Plester & Wood, 2009; Becker, 2007).

Communicating. Parent engagement in terms of communicating is interpreted as high extent (Table 2). Parent-teacher conference is an event for communication that parents commonly meet the teachers of their children (Lemmer, 2012).

Table 2
Mean distribution of parents' engagement in terms of communicating. (n=260)

Communicating	Composite Mean	Interpretation
The parents met their children's teacher during a parent-teacher conference.	3.21	High Extent
The parents read the school newsletter or school's online publication.	3.28	Very High Extent
The parents take the initiative in contacting the teacher of their children.	3.37	Very High Extent
The parents can contact the teacher of their children if they have any questions pertaining to their children.	3.48	Very High Extent
The parents receive information regarding their children's educational/academic progress from their teacher and/or homeroom teacher.	3.38	Very High Extent
Total	3.34	Very High Extent

*Legend: 1=Very low extent (1.00-1.75); 2=Low extent (1.76-2.50); 3=High extent (2.51-3.25); 4=Very high extent (3.26-4.00)

In Article 77 of Presidential Decree No. 603, it is written that parent-teacher conference is an event that allows the parents and teachers of the students to discuss the educational performance of the learners such as their participation in school programs and whenever there are issues and problems that needs to address. Constant communication and update from parents and teachers establish good rapport in the school community. Preventive measures are established because of the updated data and information gathered from teachers and parents (Kroth and Edge, 2017). However, Carbonaro (2014) argues that some teachers did receive trainings and workshops on how to work collaboratively with the parents. Hornby and White (2010) also emphasizes the importance of developing the skills of the teachers to efficiently collaborate with the parents in the learning process of their children.

The learning continuity of students at home is supported by authentic communication and relationship between parents and teachers (Carbonaro, 2014). School newsletter and online publications are some of the most pervasive methods for parents to have home-school communication (Hiatt-Michael, 2001). Communication allows parents and teachers to share information about the learning progress of the students which serve as basis on what interventions and improvements can be done to improve the learning performance of the learners (Miguel et. al., 2021). Carbonaro (2014) argued in his paper that parents actively engage themselves if they feel that they belong and being supported with their concerns and problems. Section 16 of Education Act (1982) states that teachers have the obligation to render reports and feedback about the learning performance of the students to their parents. Kraft and Rogers (2014) argues that teachers and parents collaboratively share data and information about the learning performance of the students both in school and at home. Parents engage better when they have sufficient data and received appropriate feedback about their children.

Volunteering. The result of the extent of involvement of the parents in terms of volunteering is also high extent (Table 3).

Table 3
Mean distribution of parents' engagement in terms of volunteering. (n=260)

Volunteering	Composite Mean	Interpretation
The parents volunteer in their children's class activities (e.g., reading, cooking, arts and crafts, etc.)	3.05	High Extent
The parents volunteer in maintaining the school facilities (e.g., garden maintenance, repainting the school along with other parents and teachers.)	3.07	High Extent
The parents volunteer in coordinating out-of-school activities.	2.91	High Extent
The parents volunteer in coordinating with the community to aid safety and operation of school programs.	3.15	High Extent
The parents volunteer in their children's school activities (e.g., education fair, foundation day).	3.25	High Extent
Total	3.09	High Extent

*Legend: 1=Very low extent (1.00-1.75); 2=Low extent (1.76-2.50); 3=High extent (2.51-3.25); 4=Very high extent (3.26-4.00)

This affirms the study of DeCusati and Johnson (2004) that some groups of parents do not actively participating and attending school

events and volunteer in classroom activities because they are relatively underappreciated and untapped resources to affect student-learning. In volunteering, the parents offer their time, effort and talents to help teachers facilitate student-learning (Johnson, 2014). Parents who volunteers to collaborate with teachers in facilitating learning inside the classroom are the unsung heroes who engage without expecting something in return aside from affecting student-learning for their children (DeCusati and Johnson, 2004). Brigada Eskwela (DepEd Order No. 24 S. 2008) is one the well-known school programs that allows the stakeholders to work together in preparation for the opening of classes. It is a program for parents and other stakeholders to give service in preparing the schools and classrooms for the students to have conducive environment for learning. Moreover, this is the event where the spirit of solidarity enlivens among teachers, parents and the community (Olaivar & Pobar, 2017). The collaborative effort among stakeholders creates big impact in the learning process of the students (Ayeni, 2011).

The effort of the parents in coordinating the school activities reduces the professional burnout of the teachers (Zedan, 2021). Collaborative involvement of parents to school programs and events adds confidence for them to engage efficiency and ignites the spirit of volunteerism in them (Lasater, 2019). In addition, Shepard and Carlson (2003) argues that parents are more willing to engage when they feel that they belong and part of the learning process of their children – the feeling of being needed and appreciated. Article 77 of Presidential Decree No. 603 declares that parents and teachers need to provide assistance and support to programs and activities that promote the well-being of the students. Parents volunteer to generate funds for school operations and to promote the school in their respective communities (Johnson, 2004). Their engagement strengthens the efficacy of the school activities by increasing the supervision of the students (Hamlin & Li, 2020). Parent volunteering develops social ties and fosters relational trust among parents,

teachers, and administrators. (Bryk & Schneider, 2002; Forsyth, Adams & Hoy, 2011).

Parents engagement happens if the culture and lifestyle of the family in congruent to the values and culture of school (Lareau, 2003). Hoover-Dempsey et al., (2005) argue that the non-engagement of parents in the learning process of their children is influenced by the following factors – being intimidated, lack of understanding of their role, have negative experience with the school, don't have harmonious relationship with the teachers and not having enough time for school matters. There are families who cannot engage in school whenever there are meetings, conferences and events because of the nature of their work (Baquedano-López, Alexander, & Hernández, 2013). Parents have the difficulty to participate and engage in school activities because of some practical constrains that they experience such as having lack of resources and conflicting work schedule (Hornby & Lafaele, 2011; Smith et al., 2011; Waanders et al., 2007; Lawson, 2003). The result shows that there is a need to strengthen the collaboration of teachers, parents and the communities in order to develop the learning environment and improve the learning performance of the students (Durisic and Bunijevac, 2017).

Learning at Home. The parent engagement in terms of learning at home is interpreted as high extent (Table 4). The engagement and participation of parents at home is a good opportunity to deepen the relationship and bonding of the family (Bhamani et. al., 2020). Home-based parent engagement supports the learning experience of their children by providing various learning activities and learning resources that support development (Marti et al., 2018).

However, there are also other circumstances to consider in the parent engagement at home especially when parents experience difficulties to cope up with the demands of educating the children at home (Dong et. al., 2020; Garbe et. al., 2020). Learning at home for students allow parents to engage and become learning

facilitators where they serve as their teachers and supervisors (Agaton & Cueto, 2021).

Table 4
Mean distribution of parents' engagement in terms of learning at home. (n=260)

Learning at Home	Composite Mean	Interpretation
The parents participate in the learning activities with their children, such as playing educational games.	3.22	High Extent
The parents and their children talk about the activities and what was learned in school.	3.49	Very High Extent
The parents help their children with homework.	3.10	High Extent
The parents help their children preparing for assessments at school.	3.12	High Extent
The parents held a discussion with their children regarding the lessons in school.	3.17	High Extent
Total	3.22	High Extent

*Legend: 1=Very low extent (1.00-1.75); 2=Low extent (1.76-2.50); 3=High extent (2.51-3.25); 4=Very high extent (3.26-4.00)

Parents are the forerunners in assisting their children in coping with the new learning environment brought by the changing normal (Wang et al., 2020). Parents are considered as partners, home facilitators, and para-teachers in the learning at home experience of students (Gevero, 2021). Parents engage in the learning process of their children by providing them a conducive learning environment (Varkey Foundation, 2019). Parents serve as role models, motivator and inspiration for their children (Lebaste, 2020; Capulso et al., 2021). Parents are partners that have active role in facilitating assessments at home (Orillosa and Magno, 2013). Parents are encouraged to support the development of learning of students at home (Orillosa and Magno, 2013). However, it can be seen in the data that there are parents who were not able to engage fully because some parents fall short in understanding the learning activities and courses taken by their children (Pek and Mee, 2020). For Sapta, Hamid and Syahputa (2018), it is concluded in their study that a number of the parents do not fully engage in the learning process of their children at home. Parents sort to tutors for their children to be assisted in their learning at home because of there are circumstances that parents no longer have time to be with their children. Ceka and Murati (2017) discuss in their study that there is a need for parents to know their role in the learning process of their children.

Decision Making. The extent of engagement for parents in terms of decision making is high extent. Parent engagement in the learning process of their children is realized also in participating in school governance (Colley, 2005). The perceptions and opinions of the parents are essential in the operation of school because these things may serve as data on how to develop the administrative and academic services offered (Haller and Novita, 2021). Parent engagement in the decision-making of schools is valuable because there are some aspects that they could offer that the school in itself cannot provide (Elbaum et al., 2016; LaRocque et al., 2011).

Table 5
Mean distribution of parents' engagement in terms of decision making. (n=260)

Decision Making	Composite Mean	Interpretation
The parents voice their opinions regarding the school and its development.	3.25	High Extent
The parents are engaged in the school's decision-making process regarding curriculum and learning strategies, school financial planning, or the recruitment of teachers and staff.	2.87	High Extent
The parents have the influence over what happens in their children's classroom, e.g., by providing suggestions regarding learning activities in class.	2.92	High Extent
The parents can contact the school committee if they need a change in their children's school.	3.13	High Extent
The parents vote for parent representatives in their children's class and the school committee.	3.11	High Extent
Total	3.06	High Extent

*Legend: 1=Very low extent (1.00-1.75); 2=Low extent (1.76-2.50); 3=High extent (2.51-3.25); 4=Very high extent (3.26-4.00)

Section 7 of Educational Act (1982) aims for schools and its stakeholders to have an avenue to discuss issues, concerns, suggestions, school programs and activities. However, other research studies argue that parents feel that schools are not actively collaborating with them (Love et al., 2017). Accordingly, Shannon-Baker et al (2020) discussed in their research that parents themselves also wanted to feel supported by the school – the need to be appreciated and needed. Parents have the difficulties in engaging themselves because they don't have much idea of the school curriculum and their roles (Kandemir, 2010). Parents are motivated and empowered to engage when they are being heard and supported to the decisions that they make for their children (Hoover-Dempsey, 2011). Williams and Sanchez (2011) discussed in their study that time poverty to be part of the activities and

events for the parents, lack of access and communication with the school, lack of financial resources and lack of awareness about the school curriculum are some of the hindering factors. Parents are seen communicating only to school if there are problems arise in the learning performance of their children (Ozgan and Aydin, 2010). Parents are preoccupied with the demands of their work that hinder them to allot time and resources for the school and their children (Bæck, 2010; Ho, 2009). The extent of parent engagement in decision-making such as communicating with the school for suggestions and recommendations is influenced by the demographic characteristic and socioeconomic status of the family (Cakir, 2017; Trainor, 2010). Parent engagement in school entails responsibility and significant stress because of bureaucracy and tensions in school (Tissot, 2011). There are circumstances where parents no longer think and feel that they are part of the decision-making process of the school – in planning and implementation of programs and activities for the learners (Fish, 2006; Leyser & Kirk, 2011; Mueller & Buckley, 2014; Whitaker, 2007 quoted in Kurth et al., 2017). In other words, parents do not see themselves having significant role in the decision-making in school (Blue-Banning et al., 2004).

Collaborating with the Community. The extent of parent engagement in terms of collaborating with the community is high (Table 6). Public libraries and museums are some establishments that made available to the public are institutions that fosters equality for learning opportunities that are not available at home (Luke et al. (2019); Hein, 2006; Miller et al., 2013). Educational establishments are intended to engage the community to learn together and strengthen their love towards learning (Lopez et al., 2016).

School-based parent engagement allows the parents to be the prime mover in empowering their children to actively participate in community-based activities. Parent engagement in the programs organized by school and the community establishes a supportive environment for the learners. This is an event that fosters collaboration among

parents, teachers and local community (Barron et al. 2013; Ching et al. 2016).

Table 6
Mean distribution of parents' engagement in terms of collaborating with the community. (n=260)

Collaborating with the Community	Composite Mean	Interpretation
The parents and their children visit the local library and museum.	2.86	High Extent
The parents encourage/take their children to participate in community-based activities within the local school community as informed by their children's teacher.	3.30	Very High Extent
The engagement of parents in cooperative programs between the school and the local community.	2.93	High Extent
The engagement of parents in celebrations with the locals in the school area that are conducted by the school.	3.03	High Extent
The engagement of parents in religious activities at their child's school.	3.26	Very High Extent
Total	3.08	High Extent

*Legend: 1=Very low extent (1.00-1.75); 2=Low extent (1.76-2.50); 3=High extent (2.51-3.25); 4=Very high extent (3.26-4.00)

Community-based activities offer distinct learnings and experiences that school and home context cannot give (Epstein et al., 2002). The support and the sense of ownership developed among the parents and the participation of the community towards providing quality education of the learners is a great asset to embrace by the school (Clark, 2007). Johnson (2004) argues in his study that community gains from good school because it improves the property value of the school and at the same time improves the way of living of those people around the vicinity of the school. The celebrations and events conducted by the school is an opportunity to strengthen its relationship with the community (Lawson & Alameda-Lawson, 2012). Section 8 of Educational Act (1982) allows parents to engage in discussion about school programs for them to be able to cooperate actively in the implementation. Moreover, engagement in school programs through authentic interactions establishes trust and respect among the stakeholders (Redding et al., 2004; Baker et al., 2016). The collaborative effort of the school, parents and the community is an indication of a good and quality education (Ammon et al., 1998 cited in Carbonaro, 2014).

DISCUSSION

The extent of family involvement in selected St. Paul Schools in terms of parenting and

communicating are very high. Parents engagement in the learning process is immanent in the realm of parenting and communicating. On the other hand, the extent of family involvement in terms of volunteering, learning at home, decision making and collaborating with the community are high. These are the aspects of parent engagement that still have rooms for improvement.

The engagement of parents in giving support to the home-learning environment and to the basic needs of the learners has the result of very high extent. Parents willfully perform their duties and responsibilities in providing support and assistance to have quality education for their children. Parent duties and responsibilities are well performed in the engagement of parents – to support their children’s education. Parents are committed to fulfill their duties and responsibilities both at home and in school. Support and assistance are given for the total well-being of their children. Communicating. The engagement of parents in terms of communicating of parents from home and workplace and teachers at school has the result of very high extent. There is synergy in communication and dissemination of information among parents, teachers and students. Communication is essential in the engagement and collaboration of parents and teachers. It is one of the key factors for parents to be efficient in their engagement by being updated on the learning performance of the students. A better line of communication between school and home paves the way for a data-driven approach of engagement.

The support given by the parents to collaborate with the school in affecting student learning has high extent. The result shows that there is still a room of improvement in strengthening the spirit of volunteerism of the parents of the Paulinian learners. Parents need to be empowered in order for them to collaboratively engage with the school. The spirit of volunteerism is something that needs to be nourished among the parents of the Paulinian learners – the development of service-oriented approach in the engagement practices of parents. Opportunities for the parents to

collaborate with the school in its operation serve as a gateway for them to actively engage voluntarily.

The parent engagement in the learning of students at home has the result of high extent. The result shows that parent engagement at home opens new opportunities and possibilities for the parents to become efficient since there were changes in the educational set-up for the learners brought by the effect of the changing normal and the integration of the usage of technology in the learning experience of the Paulinian learners. Learning at home improves the learning capabilities of students. Parent engagement in the learning process of the students at home fosters continuity of learning outside school. The development of home learning environment has significant improvement in the learning performance of students.

The engagement of parents in terms of participating in decision-making for school activities and programs for the learners has the result of high extent. The empowerment of parents in engaging themselves in the decision-making develops the sense of ownership and responsibility towards providing quality education to the Paulinian learners. Besides, parents are considered as partners in the implementation of the curriculum. The engagement of parents in the decision-making of schools empowers them to have the sense ownership and responsibility in providing quality education for the learners. Parents are viewed as collaborators in putting the curriculum into practice. The representation of parents in the decision-making introduces new perspectives and new opportunities for growth. Collaborating with the Community. The extent of collaboration made by the stakeholders with the community is high. The engagement of parents in outsourcing and collaborating with the community is helpful for the school to be efficient in its operation and at the same time for the betterment of the learning experience of the students. Hence, parents play a vital role in the learning experience of the students at home and in school. Collaborating with the community strengthens the parent engagement and the

operation of schools in affecting student-learning. Community serves as an extension of learning of the students. The outsourcing of experts from the field and the maximization of learning space provided by the government, private organizations and church communities intensify the learning experience of the students.

As a result of this research study, it is recommended to implement programs for parents that will foster a spirit of volunteerism and involve them in decision-making. These programs will serve as an avenue for parents to contribute to the institution's efforts to provide quality education to learners. Similarly, in the context of learning at home and collaboration with the community, programs should be developed to empower both parents and community members in creating an environment that supports students throughout their learning process.

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